

EGU24-12368, updated on 26 Nov 2024
<https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-12368>
EGU General Assembly 2024
© Author(s) 2024. This work is distributed under
the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 License.

The deployment of an integrated suite for wildfire prediction, near real-time fire monitoring and post-event mapping over Attica region, Greece.

Nikolaos S. Bartsotas, Stella Girtsou, Alexis Apostolakis, Themistocles Herekakis, and Charalampos Kontoes

National Observatory of Athens, Operational Unit BEYOND Centre, Institute for Astronomy, Astrophysics, Space Applications & Remote Sensing (IAASARS), Athens, Greece (nbartsotas@noa.gr)

In a changing climate, the growing frequency and intensity of wildfires requires innovative services in order to efficiently remediate against their catastrophic socioeconomic threat. Under the framework of MedEWSa project, we capitalise upon the reliability of the FireHub platform to further enhance its capability and features along the full spectrum of pre-event to post-event time scales, catering: (i) prevention and preparedness, (ii) detection and response, as well as (iii) restoration and inducement of cascading effects.

During the pre-event stage, the fire risk over Attica Region is denoted on a daily basis in 5 risk levels over a detailed 500m grid spacing through a combination of high resolution numerical weather predictions, advanced ML models that utilize historic wildfire record analysis as well as a number of associated atmospheric parameters (temperature, wind speed and direction, precipitation, dew point) and datasets (DEM, land use / land cover) from 2010 onwards. During the event, continuous monitoring is provided through MSG/SEVIRI image acquisitions every 5 minutes from NOA's in-house antenna, while the spatiotemporal fire-spread information is simulated through a dynamic modelling of the evolving fire. This feature is currently being further developed in order to be capable of performing "hot" starts along the incident and re-estimate based upon new hotspot retrievals from VIIRS imagery. Finally, the procedure of post-event burnt-scar mapping is currently being automated, to provide rapid footprints of the affected areas by utilising MODIS, VIIRS and Sentinel imagery and examine potential cascading effects through hazard assessment maps on landslides, soil erosion and floods. The whole suite will be hosted on a brand new fully responsive user interface that will provide detailed yet straightforward and easy to adopt information in order to enhance the decision making of policy makers and public bodies.